

A FRACTURE ANALYSIS MODEL FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER COMBINED LOADING

Erian A. Armanios and Jian Li
School of Aerospace Engineering
Georgia Institute of Technology
Atlanta, Georgia 30332

ABSTRACT

A simple analytical formulation is used to predict the interlaminar stresses of symmetric laminate under combined loading. The method is based upon a shear deformation theory and a sublaminar approach. The solution is obtained in closed form and controlling parameters are isolated. Extensive comparisons with a finite element solution are made to verify the model for the case of laminates subjected to torsion loading. An assessment of the induced curvature predicted from classical lamination theory and the present approach is provided. The influence of the induced curvature on the interlaminar stress prediction is investigated. The interlaminar stresses in laminates subjected to combined loading is obtained by superposition.

KEYWORDS: Composites, Interlaminar Stress, Free Edge Delamination, Fracture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have played an important role in achieving overall performance improvements in advanced structures. However, these are often limited by delamination resulting from interlaminar stresses. An example is the flapping flexure region of the Bell 680 rotor hubs. In addition to axial centrifugal force, the composite rotor flexure is also subjected to bending and torsion loading. The interlaminar stresses induced by these loads can cause edge delamination.

It is well documented that interlaminar stresses arise at the free edges of laminate under uniform extension and delamination caused by interlaminar stresses can initiate at the free edges in these structures. However, there are very limited work on bending, torsion and combined loadings. Salamon[1,2] predicted the interlaminar stresses in a four layer $[\pm 45]_S$ and $[\theta, 0]_S$ laminates

under uniform bending using a finite difference approach to solve the exact elasticity equations. He found that the interlaminar shear and normal stresses rise sharply near the free edges. Armanios and Rehfield[3] studied bending and combined bending and extension using a transverse shear deformation theory and a sublaminar approach for laminate layups where Mode III is negligible such as $[0_2n/90_n]_S$ and $[0_4n/(\pm 45)_n]_S$ laminates. Interlaminar stresses were obtained in closed form. Ye and Yang[4] developed a quasi-three-dimensional finite element procedure to investigate the free edge effects in symmetric composite laminates of finite width under bending. Results were presented for angle-ply $[\pm 45]_S$ and symmetric cross-ply laminates. Since the twisting effect induced by bending was not considered, their solution can only be used for those symmetric laminates where twisting and bending coupling effects are negligible. Chan and Ochoa[5,6] calculated the interlaminar stresses in symmetric laminates with various layups subjected to bending and torsion.

Kurtz and Whitney[7] developed an exact elasticity solution for simple torsion of cross-ply laminates. Comparison of this solution with the existing elasticity theory for the torsion of homogeneous orthotropic bars[8] showed that the homogeneous solution is sufficiently rigorous for most practical applications. Murthy and Chamis[9] used a three dimensional finite element analysis to investigate the width and loading conditions effects on the free-edge stress fields in composite laminates. They found that axial extension produces the smallest magnitude of interlaminar free edge stress compared to other loading conditions. Daniel and Vizzini[10] calculated the interlaminar stresses in a $[0/90]_S$ and $[\pm 15]_S$ laminate under torsion using the MSC/NASTRAN anisotropic solid elements. In contrast to the results of Ref. 7, they reported non-zero interlaminar normal stress in $[0/90]_S$ laminate.

It is seen that limited work has been devoted to the analysis of laminates under torsion, bending and their combined effects. Moreover, closed form type models used for parametric studies are not available for generally symmetric laminates subject to torsion and bending. The objective of this work is to develop a simple analytical model that provides accurate estimates of the interlaminar stresses in composite laminates under combined loading. Improvements in the delamination strength of these structures are achieved by identifying the critical interfaces and using design concepts that minimize interlaminar stresses.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

In this analysis, the interlaminar stresses are estimated based upon a displacement field that includes shear deformation and a sublaminar approach. Shear deformation is significant in composites because of their high extensional to shear modulus ratios. The sublaminar approach is particularly useful in fracture analysis where regions around the crack can be grouped into several laminated units or sublaminae and thus avoid the complexity of a ply-by-ply modeling. It has been validated by comparison of predictions with finite element simulation in Ref. 11 for laminates under uniform extension. Further simplification is achieved in the analysis by neglecting thickness strain. In this case, the interlaminar peel stress is estimated by

enforcing equilibrium and boundary conditions on transverse shear resultant as described in Ref. 12.

The generic laminate shown in Fig. 1 is subjected to combined extension F , torsion T and bending moment M . The laminate is considered as made of sublaminates or groups of plies that are conveniently treated as single laminated units. The assumed displacement field within each sublaminate may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= \epsilon_o \cdot x + \kappa \cdot x \cdot (z + \delta) + U(y) + z \cdot \beta_x(y) \\ v(x, y, z) &= V(y) + z \cdot \beta_y(y) + C \cdot x \cdot (z + \delta) \\ w(x, y, z) &= -\frac{1}{2} \kappa \cdot x^2 - C \cdot x \cdot (y + \rho) + W(y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where u , v , and w denote displacements relative to the x , y , and z axes, respectively. Axial extension and bending curvature are denoted by ϵ_o and κ . The relative angle of rotation about the x -axis is C . The arbitrary constants δ and ρ are to be determined from continuity of displacements between sublaminates and from the overall boundary conditions. Shear deformation is recognized through the rotations β_x and β_y .

The corresponding strains are

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= \epsilon_{xx}^o + z\kappa_x & \epsilon_{yy} &= \epsilon_{yy}^o + z\kappa_y & \epsilon_{zz} &= 0 \\ \gamma_{xy} &= \gamma_{xy}^o + z\kappa_{xy} & \gamma_{yz} &= \gamma_{yz}^o & \gamma_{xz} &= \gamma_{xz}^o \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where partial differentiation is denoted by a comma. The strain components associated with the reference surface are denoted by superscript o . These are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx}^o &= \epsilon_o + \kappa \cdot \delta & \epsilon_{yy}^o &= V_{,y} & \gamma_{xy}^o &= U_{,y} + C \cdot \delta \\ \kappa_x &= \kappa & \kappa_y &= \beta_{y,y} & \kappa_{xy} &= \beta_{x,y} + C \\ \gamma_{yz}^o &= \beta_y + W_{,y} & \gamma_{xz}^o &= \beta_x - C \cdot (y + \rho) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The constitutive relationship can be written as resultant forces and moments in terms of strains and curvatures as follows

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx}^o \\ \epsilon_{yy}^o \\ \gamma_{xy}^o \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_y \\ Q_x \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{yz}^o \\ \gamma_{xz}^o \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For a sublaminate of thickness h , the stiffness coefficients are defined as

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{Q}_{ij}(1, z, z^2) \cdot dz \quad (6)$$

where \bar{Q}_{ij} are the transformed reduced stiffnesses as defined in Ref. 13.

The equilibrium equations can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} N_{xy,y} + t_{2x} - t_{1x} &= 0 \\ N_{y,y} + t_{2y} - t_{1y} &= 0 \\ Q_{y,y} + p_2 - p_1 &= 0 \\ M_{xy,y} - Q_x + \frac{h}{2} \cdot (t_{2x} + t_{1x}) &= 0 \\ M_{y,y} - Q_y + \frac{h}{2} \cdot (t_{2y} + t_{1y}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the interlaminar shear and peel stresses at the sublaminates upper and lower surfaces are denoted by t_{2x} , t_{2y} , p_2 and t_{1x} , t_{1y} , p_1 , respectively.

3. INTERLAMINAR STRESSES

A solution for a laminate subject to torsion loading is sought first. With minor modifications, it can be apply to laminate under bending. A complete solution for combined loadings can be obtained by superposition. Considering the antisymmetry nature of the loading, one half of the cross section is modeled by using two sublaminates referred to as sublaminate 0 and sublaminate 1 as shown in Fig. 2. The continuity of displacements at the interface between the sublaminates are

$$\begin{aligned} u_0(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2}) &= u_1(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) \\ v_0(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2}) &= v_1(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) \\ w_0(x, y, \frac{h_0}{2}) &= w_1(x, y, -\frac{h_1}{2}) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

At the laminate central plane

$$\begin{aligned} u_0(x, y, -\frac{h_0}{2}) &= 0 \\ v_0(x, y, -\frac{h_0}{2}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

To suppress the rigid body motion of the laminate, it is assumed that the center of the laminate is fixed. That is for $x=y=z=0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} u &= v = w = 0 \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eq. 1 into Eqs. 8 and 9, and considering the conditions in Eq. 10, we have

$$\delta_1 = h_0 + \frac{h_1}{2} \quad \delta_0 = \frac{h_0}{2} \quad \rho_1 = \rho_0 = 0 \quad (11)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} U_0 &= \frac{h_0}{2} \beta_{x0} & U_1 &= h_0 \beta_{x0} + \frac{h_1}{2} \beta_{x1} \\ V_0 &= \frac{h_0}{2} \beta_{y0} & V_1 &= h_0 \beta_{y0} + \frac{h_1}{2} \beta_{y1} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where h_1 and h_0 are the thickness of sublaminates 1 and 0, respectively. The subscripts in Eqs. 11, 12 and the equations to follow refer to the respective sublaminate.

The response associated with sublaminate 0 and 1 is coupled through the interface continuity conditions. The upper surface of sublaminate 1 is stress free. The shear and peel stresses at the bottom surface will be denoted by t_x , t_y , and p , respectively. From reciprocity of stresses at the interface between sublaminate 1 and 0, the stresses at the upper surface of sublaminate 0 are t_x , t_y , and p . From the antisymmetric condition at the sublaminate bottom surface, the peel stress is zero. The interlaminar shear stresses at the bottom surface are denoted by t_{1x} and t_{1y} for sublaminate 0.

There are five boundary conditions at each sublaminate free edge, namely,

$$N_{xyi}|_{y=\pm b} = 0, \quad M_{xyi}|_{y=\pm b} = 0, \quad N_{yi}|_{y=\pm b} = 0, \quad M_{yi}|_{y=\pm b} = 0, \quad Q_{yi}|_{y=\pm b} = 0 \quad (13)$$

where i refers to the respective sublaminate: 1 or 0. The laminate sem-width is denoted by b .

By using the kinematic relations provided in Eq. 12, these boundary conditions reduce to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{h_i}{2} N_{xyi}|_{y=\pm b} + M_{xyi}|_{y=\pm b} &= 0 & \frac{h_i}{2} N_{yi}|_{y=\pm b} + M_{yi}|_{y=\pm b} &= 0 \\ Q_{y1} + Q_{y0}|_{y=\pm b} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Apply equilibrium Eq. 7 to sublaminate 1 and 0, and prescribe the boundary conditions in Eq. 14 at the sublaminate free edges, the interlaminar stresses are given as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_x \\ t_y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_{66} & h_0 A_{66}^1 & h_{26} & h_0 A_{26}^1 \\ h_{26} & h_0 A_{26}^1 & h_{22} & h_0 A_{22}^1 \end{bmatrix} \{\beta\}_{,yy} \quad (15)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} h_{ij} &= B_{ij}^1 + \frac{h_1}{2} A_{ij}^1 & h_{dij} &= D_{ij}^1 + \frac{h_1}{2} B_{ij}^1 \\ c_{ij} &= B_{ij}^0 + \frac{h_0}{2} A_{ij}^0 & h_{dij} &= D_{ij}^0 + \frac{h_0}{2} B_{ij}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and $\{\beta\} = \{\beta_{x1}, \beta_{x0}, \beta_{y1}, \beta_{y0}\}^T$.

4. VERIFICATION OF PREDICTIONS

The present theory is applied to the prediction of interlaminar stresses in unidirectional and angle-ply laminates with $[45]_{4T}$ and $[45,-45]_s$ layups, respectively. A comparison of these predictions with the finite element method (FEM) of Ref. 13 is presented in Figs. 3-6. The

laminate geometry and material properties used in the FEM model are given in Table I for convenience. The applied twist $C=0.5$ rad/in (0.02 rad/mm). The comparisons in Figs. 3-6 show that the interlaminar stresses are in good agreement with the FEM solution.

The induced bending curvature due to twist was estimated in Ref. 14 from classical lamination theory (CLT). In the CLT however, all four edges of the laminate are assumed to be subjected to torsion and consequently the free edge boundary conditions along the unloaded edges is not enforced. In the present approach the induced bending curvature is calculated based upon satisfying the stress free boundary condition along the unloaded edge. A comparison between the induced bending curvature predicted by the present approach and the CLT method of Ref. 14 is provided in Table II for four laminates. The CLT prediction is denoted by κ_c and the twist per unit length by C . The CLT predictions are in good agreement with the present approach for laminates with small thickness to width ratio (h/b). This is because the free edge boundary zone is small and consequently CLT prevails in a larger portion of the laminate. However, the CLT overestimates the induced bending curvature by 23.5 % relative to the present approach for $[45_2, -45_2]_{2s}$ laminate and 22.6 % for $[45_2, -45_2, 0_2, 90_2]_s$ laminate. Although the difference in the induced bending curvature is significant in these laminates, its influence on the interlaminar stress is small due to the fact that the induced bending curvature is small relative to the applied twist. This is shown in Fig. 7 where the shear stress distribution in the $[45_2, -45_2]_{2s}$ laminate is predicted based on κ and κ_c .

The interlaminar stress distribution in laminates subjected to extension, bending and torsion is obtained by superposition. As an example, Figs. 8-9 show the interlaminar stress distributions at the 0/45 interface for a $[0_2, \pm 45]_s$ laminate under bending, torsion and combined bending and torsion. The applied bending curvature $\kappa=1$ rad/in (0.04 rad/mm) and the twist $C=0.5$ rad/in (0.02 rad/mm). The shear stress distribution appears in Fig. 8 while the peel stress distribution is provided in Fig. 9. It is worth noting that the peel stress at the free edge of the 0/45 interface is compressive when the laminate is subjected to uniform extension. Figures 8-9 show the interlaminar stress distribution in the upper half of the laminate. The interlaminar shear stress distribution is symmetric about the mid-plane of the laminate while the peel stress distribution is antisymmetric. Consequently the peel stress distribution in Fig. 9 is tensile in the lower half of the laminate.

5. CONCLUSION

A simple analytical formulation is developed for the analysis of laminated composites subjected to combined extension, bending and torsion loading. Closed form expressions for the interlaminar stresses are obtained. The analysis is applied to unidirectional and angle-ply laminates subjected to torsion loading. The interlaminar stress predictions are in good agreement with a finite element solution.

Comparisons between the induced curvature predicted from classical lamination theory and the present approach show significant differences for laminates with thickness up to 16 % of the

width. However, its effect on the interlaminar stress prediction is negligible for the laminates considered in this study. Superposition is used to predict the interlaminar stresses in laminates subjected to combined loading.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was sponsored by the Army Research Office under Grand DAAL 03-88-C-0003 (the Center of Excellence for Rotary Wing Aircraft Technology). This support is gratefully acknowledged. The authors would also like to thank Dr. Wen Chan of the University of Texas at Arlington for providing the FEM results used in the comparisons.

REFERENCES

- [1] Salamon, N. J., "A Finite-difference Program for Stresses in Anisotropic, Layered Plates in Bending," NASA TN D-8059, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 1975.
- [2] Salamon, N. J., "Interlaminar Stresses in a Layered Composite Laminate in Bending," *Fibre Science and Technology*, Vol. 11, 1978, pp. 305-317.
- [3] Armanios, E. A. and Rehfield, L. W., "Interlaminar Fracture Analysis of Composite Laminates Under Bending and Combined Bending and Extension," *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Eighth Conference)*, ASTM STP 972, J. D. Whitcomb, Eds., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1988, pp.81-94.
- [4] Ye, L. and Yang, B. X., "Interlaminar Stress Analysis in Symmetric Composite Laminates Under Bending," Proceedings of International Conference on Computational Mechanics, May 25-29, 1986, edited by G. Yagawa and S. N. Atluri.
- [5] Chan, W. S. and Ochoa., O. O., "An Integrated Finite Element Model of Edge-Delamination Analysis for Laminates due to Tension, Bending, and Torsion Loads," Proceedings of the AIAA/ASME/AHS 28th Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Material(SDM) Conference, 1987, AIAA Paper No. 87-0704CP, Part 1, pp. 27-35.
- [6] Chan, W. S. and Ochoa, O. O., "Assessment of Free-Edge Delamination Due to Torsion," Proceedings of the Second Technical Conference, American Society for Composites, Lancaster, 1987, pp 469-478.
- [7] Kurtz, R. D. and Whitney, J. M., "Torsion of Laminates Containing Orthotropic Layers," Proceedings of the Third Technical Conference, American Society for Composites, Lancaster, 1988.
- [8] Lekhnitskii, S. G., Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Body, Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco, 1963.
- [9] Murthy, P. L. N. and Chamis, C. C., "Free-Edge Delamination: Laminate Width and Loading Conditions Effects," *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, JCTRE, Vol. 11, No. 1, Spring 1989, pp 15-22.

- [10] Daniel, W. K. and Vizzini, A. J., "Interlaminar Stresses in Composite Laminates Under Torsional Loading," Proceedings of the Fourth Technical Conference, American Society for Composites, Virginia, 1989, pp 974-981.
- [11] Armanios, E. A. and Rehfield, L. W., "Sublaminar Analysis of Interlaminar Fracture in Composites: Part II--Applications," *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, Vol. 11, No. 4, Winter 1989, pp. 147-153.
- [12] Armanios, E. A. and Badir, A. M., "Hygrothermal Influence on Mode I Edge Delamination in Composites," *Composites Structures*, Vol. 15, No. 4, 1990, pp. 323-342.
- [13] Vinson, J. R. and Sierakowski, R. L., The behavior of structures composed of composite materials, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 1986.

Table I. Material Properties of Graphite/Epoxy

$E_{11}=19.3$ Msi (133.07 GPa)
 $E_{22}=E_{33}=1.62$ Msi (11.17 GPa)
 $G_{12}=G_{23}=G_{13}=1.02$ Msi (7.03 GPa)
 $\nu=0.228$
 Ply thickness $H=0.0052$ in (0.132 mm)

Table II. Induced Bending Curvature

Stacking sequence	$\kappa_c/2C$	$\kappa/2C$	$(\kappa-\kappa_c)/\kappa$ %	h/b
[45] _{4T}	-0.3923	-0.3829	2.5	2/51
[45,-45] _s	-0.2942	-0.2832	3.9	2/51
[45 ₂ ,-45 ₂] _{2s}	-0.1471	-0.1191	23.5	8/51
[45 ₂ ,-45 ₂ ,0 ₂ ,90 ₂] _s	-0.0816	-0.0665	22.6	8/51

FIG. 1. Laminate Configuration and Loading

FIG. 2. Sublaminate Model and Coordinate System

FIG. 3. Interlaminar Normal Stress Distribution Across the Width of a $[45]_4T$ Laminate

FIG. 4. Interlaminar Shear Stress Distribution Across the Width of a $[45]_4T$ Laminate

FIG. 5. Interlaminar Normal Stress Distribution Across the Width of a $[45, -45]_s$ Laminate

FIG. 6. Interlaminar Shear Stress Distribution Across the Width of a $[45, -45]_s$ Laminate

FIG. 7. The Influence of Induced Bending Curvature on Present Approach for $[45_2, -45_2]_{2s}$ Laminate

FIG. 8. Interlaminar Shear Stress distribution Across the Width at the 0/45 Interface of a $[0_2, 45, -45]_s$ Laminate

FIG. 9. Interlaminar Normal Stress distribution Across the Width at the 0/45 Interface of a $[0_2, 45, -45]_s$ Laminate

